

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DETECTION AND GRADING OF MITRAL REGURGITATION USING R-CNN

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Abstract

Mitral regurgitation is among the most prevalent valvular pathologies, with incidence rising with age. If left untreated, severe mitral regurgitation carries a substantial risk of cardiovascular complications and mortality, including heart failure, arrhythmias, and pulmonary hypertension. Transthoracic echocardiography remains the primary noninvasive diagnostic tool; however, its interpretation relies heavily on expert experience and requires considerable time investment.

This study aims to develop a fully automated system utilizing deep learning techniques for the detection and severity assessment of mitral regurgitation in color Doppler echocardiography images.

A deep learning-based automated pipeline was developed to detect and stratify the severity of mitral regurgitation (MR) using a large dataset of apical four-chamber and apical two-chamber echocardiogram videos with color Doppler imaging of the mitral valve (Emergency Cardiology Center). Echocardiographic data collected between 2017 and 2025, comprising over 3,600 videos, were used to obtain 761 annotated images.

The model was trained in the MATLAB environment utilizing the R-CNN architecture. Detection and severity assessment of mitral regurgitation were conducted using deep learning methods implemented in MATLAB, with a focus on computer vision techniques.

Test results demonstrated greater than 95% accuracy in mitral regurgitation detection and over 80% accuracy in classification. These findings suggest that integrating artificial intelligence substantially reduces analysis time and enhances clinical decision-making.

Keywords: Mitral regurgitation, Echocardiography, Deep learning, R-CNN, Computer vision, Artificial intelligence.

Introduction

Heart disease often worsens over time without noticeable symptoms, making it difficult, if not impossible, to reverse. Regular cardiac imaging provides essential physiological insights that lead to improved patient outcomes.

Mitral regurgitation is a common heart valve disorder, and its incidence increases with age. Without treatment, severe mitral regurgitation can lead to complications such as cardiac arrhythmias and a higher risk of death. The severity of mitral regurgitation is unevenly distributed, with milder cases more common than severe ones. Accurate assessment of mitral regurgitation severity is essential for preoperative evaluation, intraoperative management, and postoperative monitoring.

Mitral regurgitation plays a crucial role in the development and progression of heart failure, both as a consequence of underlying heart disease and as a catalyst for further cardiac deterioration. It causes retrograde blood flow into the left atrium during systole, leading to volume overload and increased left ventricular pressure, which, over time, results in muscle weakness, dilation, and failure.

Accurate diagnosis of mitral regurgitation requires a comprehensive assessment using echocardiography and Doppler imaging. Transthoracic echocardiography is the primary imaging method for diagnosing mitral regurgitation because it is safe, non-invasive, and effi-

cient. Assessment of mitral regurgitation largely depends on clinicians' subjective judgement, which can lead to high labour costs, poor reproducibility, and inconsistency. Image segmentation techniques can address these issues by enabling automatic, precise delineation of regurgitation areas. Accurate segmentation improves ultrasound image analysis, aids lesion identification and localisation, and supports early detection and treatment of mitral regurgitation.

This study presents the development and validation of a fully automated deep learning method for identifying images from colour Doppler echocardiography videos and for detecting clinically significant (moderate or severe) mitral regurgitation in transthoracic echocardiograms.

In recent years, artificial intelligence has been increasingly applied in ultrasound medicine, particularly in cardiovascular disease. Despite these advances, limited research has examined the use of AI to assess the severity of mitral regurgitation (MR) from transthoracic echocardiography (TTE). Existing studies primarily focus on two areas: classification of MR severity and segmentation of the MR region. In this study, a Region-Based Convolutional Neural Network (R-CNN) was employed for the automatic qualitative assessment of MR.

Data acquisition and preprocessing

Ultrasound images were collected from the emergency cardiology centre, resulting in a dataset of 761 apical four-chamber colour Doppler echocardiograms

labelled as “mitral regurgitation.” The Department of Echocardiography acquired these images between January 2017 and July 2025.

To enhance presentation and facilitate annotation, the collected colour Doppler echocardiograms were converted from DICOM format to AVI file. From each video, frames that most accurately depicted regurgitation were selected. All images were standardized by defining sectors as regions of interest (ROI). Mitral regurgitation (MR) regions in all relevant frames were annotated using imageLabeler .

The dataset includes 121 images with mild mitral regurgitation (MR), 191 with moderate MR, and 449 with severe MR. Low-quality or unclear images, as well as data from cases with easily overestimated eccentric MR, were excluded during data acquisition. All

images were acquired using a Siemens ultrasound system and stored in DICOM format.

The annotation process combines cardiologist expertise with machine learning requirements to ensure the generation of high-quality ground truth data. Quality control is achieved through multi-expert review, which reduces inter-observer variability. The resulting dataset enables the training and evaluation of computer vision models for both localization and severity classification tasks. This framework establishes the feasibility of using region-based convolutional neural networks for automated assessment of mitral valve pathology and lays the groundwork for the advancement of AI-assisted cardiac imaging tools.

Figure 1: Ultrasound pictures from ultrasound videos

This approach employs computer vision techniques and a Region-based Convolutional Neural Network (R-CNN) to detect and assess the severity of Mitral Regurgitation in echocardiographic images. The dataset comprises color Doppler echocardiography frames, which clinical experts have annotated with bounding boxes to localize the regurgitant jet and assigned corresponding severity labels (mild, moderate, severe).

Before training, all images were resized and normalized to maintain consistency. The R-CNN model was then trained in a supervised manner, using the annotated bounding boxes as ground truth for both object localization and severity classification.

Model Training

A computer vision-based approach utilizing a Region-based Convolutional Neural Network (R-CNN) was employed to detect and classify Mitral Regurgitation in echocardiographic images. Expert-annotated images generated with the MATLAB Image Labeler tool supplied bounding box regions of interest (ROIs) and corresponding severity labels (mild, moderate, severe).

The dataset was partitioned into training and testing subsets to facilitate unbiased evaluation. During training, images were processed through the R-CNN framework to predict both the location of the regurgitant jet and its severity class. Model optimization utilized a combination of classification and localization loss functions, which enabled simultaneous learning of object detection and severity assessment.

An object detector utilizing the R-CNN architecture was implemented, offering the following capabilities:

- * Object Detection
- * Classification

This study employed a computer vision-based machine learning approach. For model training, regurgitation was annotated in the dataset using the Matlab imageLabeler tool.

The region of interest (ROI) was defined using color-coded quadrilateral polygons: orange for mild regurgitation, purple for moderate regurgitation, and green for severe pathology.

Figure 2. ROI Label 3 Color

The model training involved multiple steps to ensure accurate identification of the regurgitation zone and its severity.

Evaluation of the Model

The model exhibited strong detection capability, achieving an accuracy greater than 90% in identifying mitral regurgitation. This outcome demonstrates that the approach reliably distinguishes pathological cases from normal or non-regurgitant samples. Furthermore,

the model achieved over 80% accuracy in classifying MR severity into mild, moderate, and severe categories, indicating robust performance across all stages of disease progression.

- Detection of mitral regurgitation: accuracy exceeding 95%
- Classification of severity: accuracy exceeding 80%.

Figure: 3 Detection of Severe Mitral Regurgitation

Conclusion

Accurate assessment of mitral regurgitation (MR) severity is critical for effective clinical management. This study employed the Mask R-CNN algorithm to qualitatively evaluate MR using color Doppler echocardiography images. The model demonstrated robust performance and accurately assessed MR severity. Integrating echocardiography images with deep learning techniques reduces analysis time and facilitates more rapid clinical decision-making. The proposed model represents a promising tool for the evaluation of MR severity.

In clinical practice, this approach could be integrated into echocardiography workflows to provide decision support during image interpretation. For instance, as a cardiologist reviews color Doppler images, the system could simultaneously highlight the suspected regurgitant jet region and suggest a severity

grade. This integration may reduce inter-observer variability, a recognized challenge in MR evaluation, particularly in borderline cases between mild and moderate severity.

In our study, we developed novel methods that use recent computer vision advances to automate key aspects of echocardiogram interpretation. The system detects mitral regurgitation and classifies its severity.

This model provides a foundation for future advancements in artificial intelligence applications in echocardiography.

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